

Real and synthetic scenarios generated for the development, training, virtual testing and validation of CCAM systems

SYNERGIES

D1.1 Project Management Plan

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Primary Author(s) Jordi Pont

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CONTRIBUTORS

Name	Organization	Name	Organization
Jordi Pont	IDI		
Judit Delgado	IDI		

FORMAL REVIEWERS

Name	Organization	Date
Michael Karner	ViF	2024-09-23
Athanasios Ballis	ICCS	2024-09-23
Luisa Andreone	CRF	2024-09-23

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1 EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The SYNERGIES Project Management Plan provides a comprehensive guide for the overall management and execution of the project, detailing the procedures to be used by the consortium to ensure its successful delivery. The main objective of this document is to establish a structured roadmap for the project team, ensuring that the project is completed on time, within budget, and in compliance with the required quality standards.

The document outlines several key management areas crucial for the project's success, including:

1. **Reporting Procedures:** Clear guidelines for continuous and periodic reporting to the European Commission (EC) are defined, ensuring transparency and adherence to the grant agreement. This includes the submission of deliverables, milestones, and financial reports.
2. **Risk Management:** A proactive risk management process is presented, focusing on identifying, assessing, and mitigating potential risks throughout the project. This includes both negative risks (threats) and positive risks (opportunities) and highlights the importance of regular updates to the risk register.
3. **Stakeholder Engagement:** The document emphasizes the involvement of various internal and external stakeholders, including project beneficiaries, affiliated entities, and associated partners. The governance structure is clearly defined, detailing roles such as the General Assembly, Steering Committee, and Advisory Board, ensuring effective decision-making and communication.
4. **Contractual Arrangements:** The plan highlights the key agreements governing the project, including the Grant Agreement with the European Commission and the Consortium Agreement between the partners. Procedures for amendments to these agreements are also outlined.
5. **Communication Framework:** Both internal and external communication protocols are established to promote effective collaboration among partners and ensure consistent messaging with external stakeholders. Tools such as SharePoint and email are designated for internal communication, while formal reporting channels with the EC are clarified.
6. **Quality Control:** The document stresses the importance of maintaining high quality across all project deliverables. A structured process for preparing, reviewing, and submitting deliverables is provided, with specific guidelines on content, format, and quality assurance.

This Project Management Plan serves as a key reference document for all consortium members, providing clear direction for project activities. By following the established procedures, the consortium aims to ensure the project's timely execution, adherence to budgetary constraints, and the delivery of high-quality outcomes that contribute to the successful deployment of Cooperative Connected and Automated Mobility (CCAM) systems.

In conclusion, this document is an essential tool for guiding the SYNERGIES project towards achieving its objectives, fostering effective collaboration, and ensuring the project is completed efficiently and successfully.

Keywords: Project Management, Risk management, quality procedures

2 INTRODUCTION

2.1 Context

The development of Cooperative, Connected, and Automated Mobility (CCAM) systems represents a transformative shift in transportation, promising safer, more efficient, and sustainable mobility. These systems rely on a combination of advanced technologies such as automation, connectivity, and real-time data exchange between vehicles, infrastructure, and other road users. As CCAM systems move closer to real-world deployment, ensuring their safety and reliability has become a critical focus for industry, policymakers, and regulators.

The key challenge in CCAM development lies in the complexity and unpredictability of real-world driving environments. Automated systems must be capable of handling diverse and often hazardous scenarios across various Operational Design Domains (ODDs), such as rural roads, urban areas, and adverse weather conditions. To address this, robust virtual testing and validation frameworks are needed. These frameworks enable CCAM systems to be tested in an extensive array of simulated scenarios before deployment, minimizing the risks and costs associated with real-world testing.

Virtual testing environments provide the ability to simulate both routine and critical edge-case scenarios that a CCAM system may encounter. By integrating real-world data and artificial intelligence-driven scenario generation, these simulations cover a wide range of conditions and challenges. This approach allows developers to thoroughly assess system performance, safety, and decision-making capabilities, ensuring the technology can operate reliably across a multitude of situations.

Validation plays a crucial role in ensuring that CCAM systems meet regulatory standards and public safety expectations. Scenario-based validation frameworks, which simulate real-world traffic and environmental conditions, provide an efficient and scalable way to test the systems under varying conditions. These tests assess the system's ability to respond to potential hazards, multi-actor interactions, and other complex driving situations, ensuring that CCAM systems are not only functional but also trustworthy and safe for widespread adoption.

The combination of rigorous development, extensive virtual testing, and thorough validation processes is fundamental to achieving the widespread adoption of CCAM systems. By advancing these areas, stakeholders can ensure that CCAM technology contributes to a safer, more efficient, and smarter transportation future.

The development and implementation of the SYNERGIES project is backed by a wealth of management expertise gained through previous projects in the field CCAM. This experience includes handling complex, multi-partner collaborations, ensuring alignment between industry stakeholders, researchers, and regulatory bodies, and effectively managing large-scale innovation projects within the EU framework. Leveraging these competencies, the SYNERGIES project has been structured to address the unique challenges associated with CCAM deployment. The management practices ensure that all project activities are coordinated efficiently, meet regulatory and safety requirements, and ultimately contribute to advancing CCAM technologies for real-world applications.

2.1.1 HEADSTART

The HEADSTART project explored the state-of-the-art safety validation approaches and procedures to define a common standard methodology for testing, validation and certification,

based on consensus building among all CCAM stakeholders. A first concept was defined in the project using virtual testing, XiL, proving ground testing and field testing, also including Key Enabling Technologies (KET).

2.1.2 SUNRISE

Evolving from the achievements obtained in HEADSTART and taking other initiatives as a baseline, it became necessary to move to the next level in the concrete specification and demonstration of a commonly accepted Safety Assurance Framework (SAF) for the safety validation of CCAM systems, including a broad portfolio of use cases and comprehensive test and validation tools.

The Safety Assurance Framework is the main element being developed in the SUNRISE project. As the following figure indicates, it takes a central role, fulfilling the needs of different automotive stakeholders that all have their own interests in using it.

Figure 1 SAF Stakeholders

As it is represented in Figure 1, the overall objective of the SUNRISE project is to accelerate the safe deployment of innovative CCAM technologies and systems for passengers and goods by creating demonstrable and positive impact towards safety, specifically the EU's long-term goal of moving close to zero fatalities and serious injuries by 2050 (Vision Zero), and the resilience of (road) transport systems. The project aims to achieve this by creating and sharing a European federated database framework centralising detailed scenarios for testing of CCAM functions and systems in a multitude of relevant test cases, based on a virtual harmonised simulation environment with standardised, open interfaces and quality-controlled data exchange.

2.2 SYNERGIES

The SYNERGIES project, funded under the Horizon Europe program (HORIZON-CL5-2023-D6-01), aims to enable the development, virtual testing, and validation of CCAM systems. This is achieved by creating a scalable European Platform that consolidates real and synthetic

scenarios, which are critical for training and validating CCAM systems. These scenarios address the diverse Operational Design Domains (ODDs) that CCAM systems operate within, ensuring robust safety validation.

The project leverages a collaborative ecosystem, bringing together over 31 partners from industry, academia, and regulatory bodies. SYNERGIES builds on prior initiatives such as SUNRISE and HEADSTART (described above) by federating scenario databases across Europe, thus enabling scenario-based safety assurance.

The platform integrates key components such as a Scenario Dataspace and a Marketplace, allowing stakeholders to access and contribute data, enhancing the coverage and representativeness of the scenarios. By addressing critical challenges such as lack of interoperability, costly development cycles, and regulatory uncertainties, SYNERGIES contributes to the acceleration of CCAM system deployment while ensuring safety and reliability.

The project also focuses on fostering AI-driven scenario extraction and generation tools, enabling continuous updates of the scenario databases, thus creating a dynamic, scalable environment for CCAM development and validation.

2.2.1 Project Objectives

The SYNERGIES project is designed to enable the development, virtual testing, and scalable validation of CCAM systems. The key objectives of the project are outlined as follows:

OBJECTIVE 1. Deliver widely accessible scenarios to stakeholders through a Scenario Dataspace: SYNERGIES aims to federate existing and newly developed scenario databases by scaling up the SUNRISE federated framework. The project will provide access to relevant test scenarios in a dynamic, permanently updated European-wide database, contributing to the efficient development of CCAM systems.

OBJECTIVE 2. Maximize usability and scenario coverage: The project will ensure that scenarios are accessible to various stakeholders. To achieve this, SYNERGIES will adopt a user-centric approach, enabling stakeholders to understand the scenarios' source, representativeness, and limitations. AI tools will be integrated to automatically extract and generate new scenarios, ensuring comprehensive coverage and trustworthiness.

OBJECTIVE 3. Develop methodologies for scenario extraction and enrichment: SYNERGIES will leverage advanced AI-supported methods to generate scenarios that encompass a wide variety of environments, including rural and urban areas. This objective aims to improve the efficiency of scenario-based validation and extend the ODD coverage.

OBJECTIVE 4. Create a Marketplace for future scenario generation tools: SYNERGIES will establish a marketplace that facilitates accessibility to scenario extraction, generation, and data processing tools. This platform will ensure the continuous scalability of the Scenario Dataspace and enable new initiatives to join, thus multiplying the project's impact.

OBJECTIVE 5. Support AI development and training: SYNERGIES aims to advance the use of AI in both data and scenario generation. The project will complement existing real-world data with AI-generated synthetic data to provide diverse and rich datasets for CCAM system validation, ensuring the systems are equipped to handle a wide variety of scenarios.

To achieve all these objectives, SYNERGIES will result in a European platform (see Figure 2) aimed at improving the development, training, virtual testing, and validation of CCAM systems.

The **SYNERGIES Platform** consists of a **Scenario Dataspace**, aligned with the European approach on data sharing and competitiveness, and **Marketplace**, to ensure continuous updates and scalability of the Dataspace.

The SYNERGIES Platform will provide the European stakeholders the needed scenarios and tools for accelerated and accepted development, training, virtual testing, and validation of CCAM systems, reducing development time and costs, increasing safety and reliability, and supporting wider adoption.

Figure 2 SYNERGIES Platform

2.2.2 Project Structure

The SYNERGIES project is structured into several interrelated Work Packages (WPs), each responsible for specific aspects of the project. These WPs collaborate to achieve the overall objectives of the project, ensuring the efficient development, testing, and validation of CCAM systems.

WP1: Coordination and Management

WP1 is responsible for the overall management and coordination of the project. It ensures that all partners are aligned and that the project's objectives are met in a timely and efficient manner. This includes administrative, financial, and technical oversight of the project activities.

WP2: Requirements Definition

This work package focuses on gathering user-centric requirements from stakeholders, such as data providers and regulatory bodies. These requirements will guide the project's technical developments, including scenario generation, data processing methodologies, and platform architecture.

WP3: Data Analysis, Collection, and Generation

WP3 is dedicated to the collection and analysis of real-world and synthetic data. It focuses on gathering data from diverse environments, such as rural and urban roads, to improve the

representativeness and scalability of scenario databases. This WP also explores new data sources, including vehicle-based sensors and stationary units.

WP4: Heterogeneous AI Data Processing Tools and Data Interoperability

WP4 creates AI-supported tools for processing heterogeneous datasets. It ensures that data from various sources can be processed and harmonized, allowing interoperability between different scenario databases. This includes tasks like ontology-based data processing, semantic compression, and data fusion.

WP5: Scenario Generation Methodology and Process

WP5 develops the methodologies needed for the identification, extraction, enrichment, and generation of test scenarios for CCAM systems. This WP plays a central role in creating both real-world and AI-generated synthetic scenarios to cover a wide range of ODDs and driving conditions.

WP6: Governance, Sustainability, and Representativeness

WP6 focuses on defining the governance structure for the scenario platform. It ensures that the platform remains sustainable, widely representative, and accessible to stakeholders. This includes managing the continuous updates of scenario data and establishing the necessary licensing and data-sharing frameworks.

WP7: SYNERGIES Platform Establishment, Testing, and Delivery

This WP is responsible for the development, integration, testing, and delivery of the SYNERGIES platform. It ensures that the platform is functional, reliable, and capable of meeting the needs of its users, including developers, regulatory bodies, and testers of CCAM systems.

WP8: Platform Evaluation

WP8 establishes an evaluation framework to assess the platform's performance. Feedback is collected from users to improve the platform's functionality and ensure it meets the needs of different stakeholders, such as automotive manufacturers, regulatory bodies, and end users.

WP9: Stakeholder Engagement

Stakeholder involvement is crucial for the acceptance and uptake of the project results. WP9 is responsible for ensuring continuous engagement with stakeholders throughout the project, including workshops, feedback sessions, and collaboration with relevant industry bodies.

WP10: Outreach and Training

WP10 maximizes the impact of the project through effective communication, dissemination, and outreach activities. This WP is also responsible for training end users on how to use the SYNERGIES platform, and for standardisation (together with WP9), ensuring its wide adoption and long-term sustainability.

In the following Figure 3, the diagram with WP connections and demos that will be developed:

Figure 3 SYNERGIES Project Structure

2.3 General comments

Other comments to consider regarding the contents of this report:

1. The Grant Agreement and Consortium Agreement serve as the primary reference documents for detailed information related to the SYNERGIES project, particularly concerning project management. As such, the content of these agreements is not extensively reiterated in this report.
2. The information provided in this document was accurate at the time of its submission. However, certain elements may become outdated due to ongoing developments within the project.
3. Although the report's title includes the term "quality," no specific section is solely dedicated to this topic. Quality is instead treated as a fundamental aspect that influences many of the management areas discussed in this report. In each of these areas, the quality of project outcomes is ensured through established procedures, such as those governing reporting, communication, and risk management.

3 REPORTING

3.1 General guidelines

When creating various documents or reports within the SYNERGIES project, such as status reports, deliverables, leaflets, papers, presentations, audit reports, or press releases, the following general guidelines should be observed:

- Ensure proper acknowledgement of EU funding by using the correct [emblem](#).
- Include the following disclaimer: ***"Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or CINEA. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them."***
- Begin each report with a clear and straightforward introduction. This should provide context and explain the objectives of the document and be accessible to non-experts.
- The content must be concise, precise, reliable, and unambiguous, based on established and reputable sources.
- Ensure the information presented is accurate and comprehensive.
- The content should be verifiable, with appropriate references included.
- Where possible, quantify data and avoid subjective terms such as "small," "large," "good," or "bad."
- Conclude each report with a summary, conclusions, recommendations, and/or proposed next steps, as applicable.

3.2 EC continuous reporting

It is the obligation of the project coordinator (IDIADA) to maintain and update the continuous reporting module of the European Commission (EC) participant portal, with the information coming from the SYNERGIES consortium on publications and dissemination activities, gender issues, achieved milestones, deliverables, critical risks, patents and other IPR issues, innovation, impact, and open data.

It is the obligation of the project partners to ensure that the relevant project members are assigned to the EC participant portal, and that they have access to the project. For that reason, all contact (legal, technical, administrative) should be modified on a regular basis by each partner by updating the corresponding module in the EC participant portal.

The following **Figure 1** **Figure 4** shows the Continuous Reporting Module of the EC participant portal, including menu items for deliverables, milestones, risks and publications.

Work Package	Deliverable No	Deliverable ID	Deliverable Name	Description	Lead Org	Type	Dissemination	Due Date	New Due Date (if applicable)	Delivery Date	Approval Date	Status
WP1	D1.1	D1	D1.1 Project Management Plan	Overall procedures to be used by the consortium...	IDR	R	PU	30 Sep 2024				Pending
WP1	D1.2	D2	D1.2 Initial Data Management Plan	Guidelines and general plan describing how data...	VUFO	DMP	PU	30 Nov 2024				Pending
WP1	D1.3	D3	D1.3 Mid-term Data Management Plan	Updated version at #18 of the guidelines and ge...	VUFO	DMP	PU	30 Nov 2025				Pending
WP1	D1.4	D4	D1.4 Final Data Management Plan	Final version at #26 of the guidelines and gene...	VUFO	DMP	PU	31 May 2027				Pending
WP1	D1.5	D5	D1.5 Initial Exploitation Plan	Initial strategy for utilizing project results...	ERT	R	PU	30 Nov 2024				Pending
WP1	D1.6	D6	D1.6 Final Exploitation Plan	Ultimate plan for leveraging project outcomes...	ERT	R	PU	31 May 2027				Pending
WP2	D2.1	D7	D2.1 Stakeholder high-level requirements	Key needs and requirements gathered from main s...	IDR	R	PU	30 Nov 2024				Pending
WP2	D2.2	D8	D2.2 Stipulates definition and technical require...	User storylines definition and technical require...	BITS4	R	PU	31 May 2025				Pending
WP2	D2.3	D9	D2.3 Future requirements and roadmaps	Exploratory research to forecast realistic futu...	HDSAC	R	PU	28 Feb 2027				Pending
WP3	D3.1	D10	D3.1 Methodology for Data Quality Assessment	Methodology to analyse quality and relevance of...	UQIP	R	PU	30 Nov 2024				Pending
WP3	D3.2	D11	D3.2 Assessment of available data from extern	Analysis of the state-of-the-art in terms of av...	KCCS	R	PU	31 May 2025				Pending
WP3	D3.3	D12	D3.3 Data Generation Report	Report on the process and results of generatin...	DLR	R	PU	31 May 2026				Pending
WP3	D3.4	D13	D3.4 Best practices for data collection includi	Evaluation using diverse traffic data sources l...	VUFO	R	PU	30 Nov 2026				Pending
WP4	D4.1	D14	D4.1 Data formats, fusion, data compression a	Design and implementation of extended data form...	AVL	R	PU	31 May 2026				Pending
WP4	D4.2	D15	D4.2 Ontology-based Semantic Data Processing	Development of ontology-based semantic data pro...	CEESAR	R	PU	30 Nov 2026				Pending

Figure 4 Continuous Reporting module on EC participant portal

EC periodic reports

The coordinator must submit to the EC, the periodic technical and financial reports set out in this section. These reports align with the Grant Agreement, and include requests for payment, and must be drawn up using the forms and templates provided in the EC participant portal.

The SYNERGIES project duration is 36 months, and includes the following official reporting periods (RP) towards the EC:

There are three official reporting periods towards the European Commission (see also Figure 5):

- RP1 – from M1 to M12: 1st June 2024 to 31st May 2025
- RP2 – from M13 to M24: 1st June 2025 to 31st May 2026
- RP3 – from M25 to M36: 1st June 2026 to 31st May 2027

The coordinator must submit to the EC the technical and financial reports. All obligatory reports towards the EC are supported by the reporting system, the coordination team will prepare this reporting by preparing templates, collecting questionnaires and ask input at the partners. All will be included in the system by IDIADA, but the partner financial figures and signature must be done by each beneficiary itself.

For the **Periodic Technical report**, all partners must report:

- Explanation of the work carried out,
- Overview of the progress,
- Update of exploitation and dissemination plan,

For the **Periodic Financial report**, each beneficiary must upload their own financial statement at the portal:

- Individual financial statement of each beneficiary.
- Actual costs, Unit costs or flat-rate costs for each budget category,
- Explanation of the use of resources and the information on subcontracting,

- Comparison of planned PMs vs used PMs in the period.

After the end of each Reporting Period, a **Review Meeting** will be organized by the Project Coordinator to present the project results of the period:

- Review Meeting 1 – M13 at Brussels
- Review Meeting 2 – M25 at Brussels
- Review Meeting 3 – M36 (Location to be confirmed)

Figure 5 SYNERGIES EC Periodic reports

In addition to the periodic report for the last reporting period, the coordinator must submit the final report within 60 days following the end of the last reporting period. The final report must include the following:

- A **Final Technical report** with a summary for publication containing:
 - An overview of the results and their exploitation and dissemination,
 - The conclusions on the action,
 - The socio-economic impact of the action.
- A **Final Financial report** containing:
 - A **final summary financial statement**, created automatically by the electronic exchange system, consolidating the individual financial statements for all reporting periods and including the request for payment of the balance and
 - A **certificate on the financial statements (CFS)** if the requested EU contribution is $\geq 430.000\text{€}$

3.3 Interim reporting

A close monitoring process will be implemented, with an **internal report** being submitted every 6 months to the Project Coordinator. This report will provide an update on the technical progress of activities in each Work Package (WP). It will summarize the work completed, highlight key achievements per task, and outline any deviations from the DoA. Task leaders or key partners involved in specific tasks may assist in preparing the report.

The internal report will also include a financial section, presenting the current status of resources used (in person-months and euros) compared to the original plan, covering direct personnel costs, subcontracting, and other direct expenses.

Table 1 Summary of internal reporting of the project

Report	Content	Responsible	Distribution
INTERNAL partner progress report (Semester) M6, M18, M30	Summary of activity across all WPs; input to dissemination actions. Effort, estimated cost	Each Partner	Internal
INTERNAL WP Reports (Semester) M6, M18, M30	Summary of progress against objectives by WP	WP Leaders	Internal

3.4 Deliverables

The preparation and submission of deliverables are main indicators of the project's progress. Work on deliverables should begin as soon as the associated task is initiated. Regular progress updates should be provided to the task and work package leaders, who will then report to the Steering Committee.

This section is intended to provide guidance for drafting, reviewing, and submitting high-quality deliverables on schedule. In addition to following the general guidelines outlined elsewhere, all SYNERGIES deliverables should include the following key elements:

- Table of contents
- List of figures
- List of tables
- Executive summary
- Introduction providing context and explaining the objective(s) of the report.
- Description of the work performed
- Dissemination, exploitation and standardisation
- Conclusions
- List of references
- Appendix (Optional)
- Abbreviations and definitions

The content items listed above, mainly apply to deliverables of technical nature. Deliverables of non-technical nature might slightly divert from these items.

For the preparation of deliverables, partners shall use the [deliverable template](#) shared on the SharePoint repository. A list informing about the deliverable reviewers is also available there.

To ensure that deliverables are of high quality and submitted on time, the submission procedure shown in the Figure 6, must be followed.

Figure 6 Deliverable submission procedure

Additional notes on the roles and responsibilities related to the submission process outlined in the figure above:

- The **deliverable leader** is responsible for defining the structure and format of the deliverable. The deliverable leader is indicated in the Grant Agreement.
- The deliverable leader ensures the deliverable is submitted on time.
- Authors are responsible for writing the content.
- The deliverable leader reviews the quality and submits the deliverable to the WP leader and designated reviewers.
- Reviewers are assigned annually during General Assembly meetings and shared in the Project Repository.
- The WP leader and reviewers check for quality, consistency, and alignment with the WP description.
- The deliverable leader and authors address the feedback and make necessary revisions.
- The deliverable leader submits the deliverable to the project coordinator, who checks overall quality before submitting it through the EC participant portal.

Some best practices for drafting, reviewing, and submitting deliverables:

- Authors should allow adequate time for feedback from the deliverable leaders, WP leaders, reviewers, and the project coordinator.
- Adhere to the deadlines for submission outlined in the DoA.
- Report any issues in the submission process, such as delays or quality concerns in advance.
- Apply internal plagiarism check on the final draft and proceed to final amendments where necessary.

4 PROJECT GOVERNANCE AND CONSORTIUM

4.1 Governance

The overall governance structure of the SYNERGIES project is shown in the following Figure 7:

Figure 7 Governance structure

The main roles and bodies of this overall governance structure are explained below.

European Commission (EC)

The European Commission serves as the politically independent executive arm of the European Union (EU). It is tasked with drafting proposals for new EU legislation and enforcing decisions made by the European Parliament and the Council of the EU.

Functioning like a cabinet government, the Commission consists of 27 members, referred to as "Commissioners," and is led by a President. The Commission is organized into departments called Directorates-General (DGs), which are like ministries or government departments. Each DG is managed by a Director-General who reports to a commissioner.

The President sets the overall policy direction for the Commission, allowing the Commissioners to collectively establish strategic goals and develop annual work programs. One of these programs is Horizon Europe, the EU's primary funding initiative for research and innovation. Horizon Europe promotes collaboration and enhances the impact of research and innovation to support EU policies and address global challenges. SYNERGIES is among the many projects carried out under this program.

CINEA

While the European Commission defines the policy, the European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency (CINEA) is responsible for putting these policies into practice. CINEA's tasks involve organizing calls for project proposals, overseeing project life cycles, monitoring the technical and financial progress of projects, and ensuring effective financial management.

Project Officer (PO)

CINEA designates project officers to each project carried out under the programs established by the European Commission. The key roles and responsibilities of a project officer include:

- Serving as the main contact for the project coordinator on matters related to technical and strategic management, as well as legal and administrative concerns.
- Acting as the project's "advocate" within the European Commission.
- Ensuring compliance with the obligations outlined in the Grant Agreement.
- Monitoring the fulfillment of contractual duties through deliverables, public reports, reviews, and other means.
- Verifying financial statements.

Advisory Board (AB)

The Advisory Board represents various CCAM-related stakeholders within the SYNERGIES project. Its members may consist of standardization bodies, CCAM user associations, policymakers, and regulators. The Advisory Board's role is to oversee the project and provide insights on stakeholder needs, regulatory compliance, relevant EU policies, societal priorities, and socioeconomic impacts.

Advisory Board members will participate in specific dissemination events, help promote project results and activities, and facilitate connections and dialogues with relevant stakeholders. Annual meetings with the Advisory Board will be held to present project progress, discuss next steps, and seek advice on potential strategic directions. These meetings will be organized as part of WP1 and attended primarily by the Steering Committee.

The current members of the Advisory Board are:

- Biaggio Ciuffo (Smart Mobility Project portfolio leader at JRC)
- Benjamin Engel (CTO at ASAM)
- Trent Victor (Director of safety Research and Best Practices at WAYMO)
- Steven Shladover (Researcher at UC Berkeley)
- Peter Burns (Chief, Human Factors and Crash Avoidance Research at Transport Canada)
- Ryan Lamm (Executive Director R&D – Robotics & AI at Southwest Research Institute (SwRI, US))

General Assembly (GA)

The General Assembly serves as the consortium's primary decision-making body, responsible for making final decisions regarding the project's overall policy, proposed changes or extensions to the Consortium Agreement, and the project's objectives.

Each consortium partner is represented by one member in the General Assembly, and all representatives have equal voting rights. The project coordinator will preside over all General Assembly meetings, and all consortium partners agree to adhere to the Assembly's decisions.

General Assembly meetings will be held every six months, with one meeting conducted online and the other held in person.

Steering Committee (SC)

The Steering Committee serves as the supervisory body responsible for overseeing the execution of the project. It reports to the General Assembly, ensuring the project is implemented efficiently and delivers the best possible outcomes. The Steering Committee is composed of WP leaders, OEM representatives and the Innovation and Exploitation Manager, with the primary role of monitoring and supervising the quality of project results.

The specific responsibilities of the Steering Committee include:

- Monitoring progress and achievements in relation to the DoA.
- Identifying and mitigating potential risks.
- Facilitating problem-solving and conflict resolution.
- Discussing and advising on strategic issues.

Project Coordinator (PC)

The Project Coordinator acts as the legal intermediary between the consortium partners and the European Commission (EC). The coordinator's responsibilities include:

- Serving as the primary contact with the EC for reporting and payments.
- Representing all beneficiaries in communications with the EC.
- Managing the financial contributions, distributing funds among the beneficiaries, maintaining financial records, and informing the EC about fund allocation.
- Reviewing reports to ensure they align with the Grant Agreement (GA) before submission.
- Monitoring beneficiaries' compliance with their obligations under the GA.

Jordi Pont and Raul Villalba from IDIADA hold the role of Project Coordinator and Technical Project Coordinator, primarily operating within WP1.

Innovation and Exploitation Manager

The Innovation and Exploitation Manager (IEM) shall guide the project to establish sound proposals based on specific technology evolution and CCAM validation maturation paths. The IEM shall coordinate actions with the SC with the aim of identifying potential candidates for early market uptake. This role is fulfilled by Stephane Dreher from ERTICO.

Intellectual Property Rights Manager

The Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) Manager provides advisory and supportive services concerning intellectual property matters within the consortium. This role includes assisting with the identification, management, and protection of intellectual property rights arising from the consortium's activities. The Intellectual Property Rights Manager advises on IP strategy, facilitates the handling of IP issues among consortium members, and ensures compliance with

applicable laws and regulations, without directly managing the IP assets. The IPR Manager only acts if the parties request assistance. This role is fulfilled by Mariola Hauke from CLEPA.

Data Protection Officer

The Data Protection Officer (DPO) provides expert advice and support on data protection matters within the consortium. The Data Protection Officer's responsibilities include advising on the consortium's compliance with data protection laws, assisting in the implementation of data protection principles and practices, and offering guidance on the management of data privacy risks. The DPO serves as a consultant, aiding in understanding and navigating data protection obligations without directly managing data protection procedures. This role is fulfilled by Dorleta García from VICOMTECH.

Liaison and Cooperation Manager

The Liaison and Cooperation Manager plays a critical role in fostering collaboration between project partners and external stakeholders, including researchers, industry leaders, and regulatory bodies. This manager ensures continuous communication with key stakeholders, incorporating their input to guide the project's progress. They also coordinate with other international initiatives to align efforts and avoid duplicating work, while actively promoting SYNERGIES outputs in global standardization efforts, such as with ISO and Euro NCAP. Additionally, the manager organizes workshops and collaborative platforms to gather feedback and integrate it into the project's development. This role is essential in maximizing the project's impact and ensuring its outcomes meet industry and regulatory expectations. This role is fulfilled by Iain Macbeth from ERTICO.

WP leaders (WPL)

The responsible for the technical management of WPs. The work package leaders are as follows:

Table 2 SYNERGIES WP leaders

WP Leaders		
Work Package	Lead	Appointed person
WP1	IDI	Jordi Pont
WP2	IDI	Raúl Villalba
WP3	ICCS	Elena Daskalaki
WP4	VICOM	Marcos Nieto
WP5	RWTH	Lenart Vater
WP6	TNO	Erwin Degelder
WP7	AVL	Iskra Gasparic
WP8	UNIGE	Riccardo Berta
WP9	ERT	Iain Macbeth
WP10	VIF	Michael Karner

Task leader (TL)

The responsible for the technical management of individual tasks within each WP. They report to the WPL on a regular basis.

4.2 Consortium

Under Horizon Europe, project participants can be assigned with one of various roles, depending on their characteristics. Depending on this role, participant have different rights and obligations under the Grant Agreement. The roles of relevance for SYNERGIES are explained in Figure 8.

Figure 8 Roles in a HE Project

Beneficiaries (BEN)

Beneficiaries are the legal entities that sign the Grant Agreement and are fully accountable to the European Commission (EC) for executing the project and adhering to all obligations outlined in the Grant Agreement. The Granting Authority covers the costs incurred by the Beneficiaries. Beneficiaries must have sufficient resources to carry out the project. If they rely on affiliated entities or other participants, they still maintain full responsibility towards both the granting authority and the other beneficiaries.

Beneficiaries shall ensure that the contractual obligations specified in the Grant Agreement are extended to any other participants (such as affiliated entities, associated partners, or subcontractors). They are required to perform the tasks outlined in the Grant Agreement, provide all requested data to the EC, and inform the EC (via the project coordinator) of any events that may impact the project's implementation.

The Beneficiaries involved in SYNERGIES are:

Table 3 SYNERGIES Beneficiaries

N°	Role	Short Name	Legal Name
1	COO	IDI	IDIADA AUTOMOTIVE TECHNOLOGY SA
2	BEN	BMW	BAYERISCHE MOTOREN WERKE AKTIENGESELLSCHAFT
3	BEN	PSA	STELLANTIS AUTO SAS
4	BEN	REN	RENAULT SAS
5	BEN	TME	TOYOTA MOTOR EUROPE NV
6	BEN	AVL	AVL LIST GMBH
7	BEN	CEESAR	CENTRE EUROPEEN D'ETUDES DE SECURITE ET D'ANALYSE DES RISQUES
8	BEN	CLEPA	ASSOCIATION EUROPEENNE DES FOURNISSEURS AUTOMOBILES
9	BEN	CTAG	FUNDACION PARA LA PROMOCION DE LA INNOVACION INVESTIGACION Y DESARROLLO TECNOLOGICO EN LA INDUSTRIA DE AUTOMOCION DE GALICIA
10	BEN	DLR	DEUTSCHES ZENTRUM FUR LUFT - UND RAUMFAHRT EV
11	BEN	ERT	EUROPEAN ROAD TRANSPORT TELEMATICS IMPLEMENTATION COORDINATION ORGANISATION - INTELLIGENT TRANSPORT SYSTEMS & SERVICES EUROPE
12	BEN	FCE	FAURECIA CLARION ELECTRONICS EUROPE
13	BEN	ICCS	EREVNITIKO PANEPISTIMIAKO INSTITOUTO SYSTIMATON EPIKOINONION KAI YPOLOGISTON
14	BEN	RWTH	RHEINISCH-WESTFAELISCHE TECHNISCHE HOCHSCHULE AACHEN
15	BEN	IRTSX	INSTITUT DE RECHERCHE TECHNOLOGIQUE SYSTEM X
16	BEN	IVEX	IVEX NV
17	BEN	MOSAIC	MOSAIC FACTOR SL
18	BEN	PAVE	PARTNERS FOR AUTOMATED VEHICLE EDUCATION EUROPE ASSOCIATION
19	BEN	RISE	RISE RESEARCH INSTITUTES OF SWEDEN AB
20	BEN	SIE-NL	SIEMENS INDUSTRY SOFTWARE NETHERLANDS BV
21	BEN	SIE-BE	SIEMENS INDUSTRY SOFTWARE NV
22	BEN	TNO	NEDERLANDSE ORGANISATIE VOOR TOEGEPAST NATUURWETENSCHAPPELIJK ONDERZOEK TNO
23	BEN	TUE	TECHNISCHE UNIVERSITEIT EINDHOVEN
24	BEN	UNIGE	UNIVERSITA DEGLI STUDI DI GENOVA
25	BEN	VICOM	FUNDACION CENTRO DE TECNOLOGIAS DE INTERACCION VISUAL Y COMUNICACIONES VICOMTECH
26	BEN	VIF	VIRTUAL VEHICLE RESEARCH GMBH
27	BEN	VUFO	VERKEHRSUNFALLFORSCHUNG AN DER TU DRESDEN GMBH

Affiliated Entities (AE)

Affiliated Entities are organizations linked to a Beneficiary that contribute to the project. They have similar rights and responsibilities as the Beneficiaries. Affiliated Entities are responsible for carrying out the tasks assigned to them in the Grant Agreement. However, Affiliated Entities do not formally sign the Grant Agreement.

The Affiliated Entities participating in SYNERGIES are:

Table 4 SYNERGIES Affiliated Entities

N°	Role	Short Name	Legal Name
1.1	AE	IDI_DE	IDIADA Fahrzeugtechnik GmbH
3.1	AE	CRF	CENTRO RICERCHE FIAT SCPA

Associated Partners (AP)

An Associated Partner is an entity that contributes to the project but is unable to declare costs and must have its own independent budget. Associated Partners are responsible for securing their own funding and resources for their part of the project.

While Associated Partners do not sign the Grant Agreement, they play a significant role in implementing key aspects of the project and are often actively involved in the consortium. As a result, the Grant Agreement acknowledges their participation and outlines their roles, rights, and obligations.

Table 5 SYNERGIES Associated Partners

N°	Role	Short Name	Legal Name
28	AP	TORC	Torc Europe GmbH
29	AP	SWRE	SCHWEIZERISCHE RUCKVERSICHERUNGSGESELLSCHAFT AG
30	AP	FEVIO	FEV IO GMBH
31	AP	UoW	THE UNIVERSITY OF WARWICK

5 RISK MANAGEMENT

5.1 Risk identification and response plans

General and specific risks are inherent in both the organization and execution of a project. For the SYNERGIES project, the Failure Mode and Effects Analysis (FMEA) method will be employed to identify potential risks, their causes, and potential effects.

Risks will be identified at the task level and evaluated based on two factors:

- **Risk Severity:** the impact of the risk on the project's success if it materializes.
- **Risk Likelihood:** the probability that the risk will occur.

Using these two factors, a risk priority number (RPN) will be calculated, and the risks will be categorized into five levels, ranging from insignificant to catastrophic. Each identified risk will be assigned to a partner, and mitigation measures will be developed based on the RPN, with the highest-priority risks receiving the most attention.

Risk reduction is an ongoing, iterative process that may involve:

- Improving the speed and likelihood of risk detection.
- Minimizing the impact of threats.
- Implementing protective measures against threats through mitigating strategies to address potential failures.

In Figure 9, there is a sample of SYNERGIES Risk Management spreadsheet.

Risk Management - Risks										
Risk Number [aligned with EC Portal]	WP	Task	Risk Title Description	Risk Severity [0-10]	Risk Likelihood [0-10]	Risk Priority Number [RPN]	Risk Importance	Risk Response	Risk Caretaker(s)	Listed on EC Portal
1	1	T1.1	Delays in project coordination and management activities.	3	2	6	Slight	Regular progress meetings, clear communication channels and contingency planning for potential delays.	IDI	Yes
2	3	T3.2-T3.5	Data quality issues in WP3 Data analysis and generation	4	2	8	Slight	Implement rigorous data quality assessment methodologies and continuous monitoring, as well as data validation and cleansing processes	ICCS	Yes
3	3	T3.1, T3.2	Qualification of data from heterogeneous sources may require rethinking of quality metrics	3	2	6	Slight	Focus on generalization of metrics in T3.1, work iteratively between T3.1 and T3.2, follow modular qualification methods	ICCS / RISE	Yes
4	3	T3.5 and potentially T3.3, T3.4	Aggregation of data from heterogeneous sources may be more time-consuming than expected	3	4	12	Slight	Work in close collaboration with WP4	ICCS / RWTH / AVL / RISE	Yes

Figure 9 FMEA Risk management sample

5.2 Risk control

The risk management process will follow these steps:

1. Task Leaders will gather a risk report from their team members at the start of the project and update this report every six months.
2. The report will then be sent to the Work Package Leader, who will review it with the Steering Committee and compile a comprehensive Work Package risk report, which will be submitted to the Project Coordinator.
3. During the Steering Committee meeting, the risk report will be evaluated, and the findings will be presented to the General Assembly and included in the Periodic Reports to the European Commission.

6 COMMUNICATION

6.1 Internal communication

6.1.1 Hierarchy

The Figure 10 illustrates the communication hierarchy that must be followed within the SYNERGIES consortium. As shown, team members should first communicate with their Task Leaders regarding any issues or concerns related to their assigned tasks. If Task Leaders are unable to resolve the issues, they should escalate them to the Work Package Leaders. Work Package Leaders can then bring any project-impacting matters to the Steering Committee, where all work package leaders are involved. Similarly, top-down communication must adhere to this same hierarchical structure.

Figure 10 Consortium internal communication hierarchy

This straightforward communication hierarchy is designed to minimize the chances of individuals being incorrectly included or excluded, along with the related issues this can cause. It is also expected to streamline overall communication, reducing the likelihood of communication-related problems.

The hierarchy outlined in the figure above applies specifically to work packages and their scope. Any communication that falls outside the scope of a work package or task does not need to follow this structure.

6.1.2 Internal meetings

SYNERGIES internal meetings are organized by the responsible partner, which may be the Project Coordinator, a Work Package Leader, or a Task Leader. Every meeting must be formally documented, and the partner leading the meeting is responsible for both the documentation and the distribution of the meeting minutes. Meetings can be scheduled periodically or on an ad-hoc basis. For meetings at the project, work package, or task level, relevant members must be informed in advance, allowing adequate time for necessary preparations.

For General Assembly meetings, the Project Coordinator is supported by the hosting partner, particularly for matters such as venue, equipment, catering, and administrative tasks. For further

details on meeting procedures, such as notification and agenda requirements, please refer to the Consortium Agreement.

The following types of internal consortium meetings are planned:

- **General Assembly (GA):** All consortium partners attend GA meetings, held every six months. The Project Coordinator coordinates the schedule for these meetings, which will alternate between physical and online formats.
- **Work Package Meeting:** These are work package-specific meetings organized by each Work Package Leader, with invitations extended to at least every Task Leader. The frequency of these meetings is determined by the respective Work Package Leaders.
- **Task Meeting:** Task-specific meetings are organized by Task Leaders, with at least one representative from each contributing partner. The frequency of these meetings is decided by the Task Leaders.
- **Ad-hoc Meetings:** These are organized as needed based on project requirements.

6.2 External communication

6.2.1 Hierarchy

The Figure 11 illustrates the communication hierarchy that must be followed between the SYNERGIES consortium and the European Commission (EC). As shown, all communication between the consortium and the EC is channelled exclusively through the Project Coordinator (IDIADA) and the Project Officer (EC). Consortium partners must present any topics or issues they wish to raise with the EC through the Project Coordinator, meaning they are not permitted to directly address these matters with the EC.

Figure 11 Communication between SYNERGIES consortium and EC Project Officer

6.3 External meetings

The following types of external meetings are planned:

- **EC Review.** The Project Coordinator, the WP leaders and the Industrial Representatives will participate in this review, with other partners attending as needed to provide specific support based on the agenda set by the EC and the content of the meeting. EC reviews are scheduled in M13, M25, and M36, with the possibility of additional ad-hoc review meetings requested by the EC. The location of the first two meetings shall be Brussels and the last one will be decided during the project execution.
- **Advisory Board Meetings.** These meetings involve a dedicated group of experts and advisors. Their purpose is to inform participants about the project's goals and progress, extend its reach and impact, and gather valuable feedback. These meetings are planned annually.
- **Vehicle Safety Body Meetings.** Regular meetings will be held to share relevant results and information with international vehicle safety bodies, such as UNECE, Euro-NCAP, ASAM, ISO, or SAE (among others). The primary objective of these meetings is to promote the adoption of SYNERGIES results by these organizations. The responsibility for achieving this goal lies with the Liaison Manager under WPg.

7 CONTRACTUAL ARRANGEMENTS

7.1 Consortium Agreement

The Consortium Agreement (CA), which is the official contract between the project partners and the coordinator, extends the provisions set in the Grant Agreement and defines the project's governance, liability between partners, responsibilities, ownership of results, access rights to third parties, non-disclosure conditions, etc. The SYNERGIES Consortium Agreement is based on the DESCA model consortium agreement for Horizon Europe.

7.2 Grant Agreement

The Grant Agreement is the official contract between the consortium and the EC. The technical and operational reference document is Annex 1 of GA - Description of the Action often referred to as DoA (Description of Action) or DoW (Description of Work). It reflects the activity plan to be carried out, in the form of work packages and tasks, as well as all the objectives, milestones and deliverables.

7.3 Amendments

Significant project changes and deviations to the DoA of the Grant Agreement are called amendments, and must be requested in writing to the EC. The work package leader that proposes the change, shall request the modification in writing to the project coordinator, and attach an explanation of the proposition, indicating a clear justification (supported by the DoA), and the consequences in terms of scope, budget, schedule, etc. This written request should clearly explain, why this change is necessary for the project. Only the project coordinator may submit requests for amendments to the EC, on behalf of the consortium.

Important to note is that amendments must not have the purpose of making changes to the agreement which might call into question the decision awarding the grant.

Changes that affect project critical aspects like scope, budget, schedule, or (human) resources, must be given priority and communicated as early as possible to the project coordinator and the affected work package leader(s). The earlier these changes are communicated, the better they can be anticipated, and the less they will affect the project. Changes are likely to occur throughout the project, but sufficient time should be reserved to react.

Certain minor changes do not require an amendment but must be communicated to the project coordinator, and the affected work package leader(s), who will inform the project officer. Some examples of changes that do not require amendments of the Grant Agreement are transfers of budget between different activities and between themselves, as long as the work is carried out as foreseen in Annex I of GA (the DoA). However, if for any reason the EC finds that the changes are not justified, the relevant costs will not be reimbursed.

The following table contains an overview of the changes that *do* and *do not* need an amendment.

Table 6 Need for amendments of the Grant Agreement

No amendment needed	Amendment needed
Budget transfers covered by the budget flexibility.	Adding a new beneficiary.
Name or address changes of a participant, done directly in the participant register.	Terminating a beneficiary's participation.
Universal take-overs (merger/acquisition) of a participant, done directly in the participant register.	Change of beneficiary due to partial take-over.
Changes of the banking details, done directly in the participant register.	Removal or addition of an affiliated entity.
"Simplified approval procedure" (documented in the periodic report/UoR at REPA stage + assessed by the project officer after submission).	Change of coordinator or bank account.
	Change of duration
	Fundamental change of scope, impact or ambition.

For the avoidance of doubt, independent of whether an amendment is needed or not, always timely and duly inform the project coordinator and the affected work package leaders, of any changes to the DoA of the Grant Agreement.

8 CONCLUSIONS

This Project Management Plan defines the overall procedures and guidelines to be followed by the SYNERGIES consortium throughout the project's execution. It establishes a clear roadmap to ensure that the project is completed on time, within budget, and meets the expected quality standards. The structured approach outlined in this document covers key areas such as reporting, risk management, stakeholder engagement, contractual agreements, and communication protocols, all of which are vital to the project's success.

By adhering to these defined procedures, the SYNERGIES team can effectively coordinate across work packages, manage risks proactively, and ensure timely delivery of all project milestones and deliverables. The robust communication framework, including both internal and external communication protocols, will help to maintain transparency and foster collaboration among partners. Furthermore, the continuous monitoring of progress and the well-established risk management plan will allow the consortium to address potential challenges and deviations efficiently.

This document also emphasizes the importance of quality control and a results-oriented approach. By implementing standardized procedures for reporting, communication, and deliverable submission, the consortium is well-positioned to meet its objectives while maintaining high standards of quality throughout the project lifecycle.

In conclusion, the effective use of this management plan will support the consortium in achieving the overarching goals of the SYNERGIES project, enabling the safe and reliable deployment of CCAM systems. The structured guidelines provided here serve as a vital tool for ensuring a coordinated, efficient, and high-quality project execution, paving the way for the successful completion of all project deliverables.

9 REFERENCES

- [1] "Manage Your Grant - IT How to - Funding Tenders Opportunities | <https://webgate.ec.europa.eu/funding-tenders-opportunities/display/IT/Manage+your+grant>
- [2] Headstart project | <https://www.headstart-project.eu/>
- [3] Sunrise Project | Developing and providing a harmonized and scalable CCAM Safety Assurance Framework. (n.d.). <https://ccam-sunrise-project.eu/>
- [4] SYNERGIES Consortium (2024). Grant Agreement.
- [5] SYNERGIES Consortium (2024). Consortium Agreement.
- [6] Nuria Parera, Valenti Prat, David Fernandez (2020). SAFE-UP D1.1: Project Management Plan
- [7] Marcos Pillado, Raúl Ferrandez, Jacint Castells (2017). C-MOBILE D1.1: Project Management, quality and risk procedures
- [8] Stefan de Vries, Jordi Pont (2022). SUNRISE D1.1: Project Management, quality and risk procedures

A. ABBREVIATIONS AND DEFINITIONS

Term	Definition
AB	Advisory Board
AD	Automated Driving
AE	Affiliated Entities
AP	Associated Partners
ASAM	Association for Standardization of Automation and Measuring systems
BEN	BENeficiaries
CA	Consortium Agreement
CCAM	Cooperative, Connected, and Automated Mobility
CFS	Certificates on Financial Statements
CINEA	Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency
DB	DataBase
DESCA	Development of a Simplified Consortium Agreement
DG	Directorates General
DoA	Description of Action
DPO	Data Protection Officer
EC	European Commission
EP	Expert Platform
EU	European Union
FMEA	Failure Mode and Effects Analysis
GA	Grant Agreement General Assembly
HEADSTART	Harmonised European Solutions for Testing Automated Road Transport
HE	Horizon Europe
IEM	Innovation and Exploitation Manager
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
ISO	International Organization for Standardization
ITS	Intelligent Transport Systems
JRC	Joint Research Center
KET	Key Enabling Technologies
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
NCAP	New Car Assessment Program
ODD	Operational Design Domain
PC	Project Coordinator
PM	Person Month
PO	Project Officer
RP	Reporting Period

RPN	Risk Priority Number
SAE	Society of Automotive Engineers
SAF	Safety Assurance Framework
SC	Steering Committee
SCDB	SCenario DataBase
SME	Small or Medium-sized Enterprise
SUNRISE	Safety Assurance Framework for Connected and Automated Mobility Systems
TL	Task Leader
TRL	Technology Readiness Level
UNECE	United Nations Economic Commission for Europe
WP	Work Package
WPL	Work Package Leader
XiL	X-in-the-Loop